

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

Govert Westerveld - Independent Researcher

Ex-Official Chronicler of the village Blanca

Fellow of the Real Academia Alfonso X el Sabio

Member of the Asociación Internacional de Hispanistas

Ex-Member of the Commission of History of the Spanish Chess Federation

Official Historian of the Fédération Mondiale du Jeu de Dames (FMJD, World Draughts Federation)

<https://govertwesterveld.academia.edu/>

© Author(s) 1996-2020.

Academia de Estudios Humanísticos de Blanca, 2020, N° 34, pp. 1-13 – June 2020 DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22043.08485

Fernando de Rojas, author del Ms. 8756 Rey Francisco I de Francia

Research by the linguistic Program

Apart from making my research with CORDE and studying the works of Rolf Eberenz, Carmen Quijada Van Den Berghe, Lola Pons Rodríguez, Ana Vian, and María Ángeles García Aranda, I also use other possibilities. For example, with stylistic methods and various text-analysis programs. In this sense we have to realize that they are quite interesting programs, but they are still not perfect. On the other hand, I do not consider myself expert in using these programs. Although my way of working has its doubts, some conclusions can be made with it for identification of authorship.

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

Text-analysis and Authorship Attribution

Authorship Attribution is a long-standing problem in text analysis, and indeed in the humanities in general. Law enforcement and forensic scientists are interested in these methods; Chaski reports on a court case where a body was discovered near a computer with an apparent suicide note typed into it. In case of a hand-written note, of course, handwriting specialists could be called in to verify that the note was in the handwriting of the deceased, but one flat-ASCII 'A' looks identical to any other. What was needed instead was an analysis based on writing style, and Chaski was able to prove that the deceased did not write the note, and a murder had been committed¹.

The authorship identification tools can help us compare texts by writers known to us from the 15th-16th century with the texts that we possess by unknown authors. We have to rely on the well-tested assumption that people have a distinct way of writing. The characteristics manifest themselves in how writers use words, spell certain words, structure sentences, and through many other individualities.

Results

As we will observe in the text-analysis in the Appendix, the idiolect of the Mss 8756 does not correspond to Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo, but to Fernando de Rojas (Appendix).

¹ **JUOLA, Patrick** (2009) JGAAP: A System for Comparative Evaluation of Authorship Attribution. In: *JDHCS*, Volume 1, Number 1, pp. 1-5

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

Appendix

The Mss 8756 Francisco I Rey de Francia

fernándezOviedoReyFrancia22kb.txt C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\fernándezOviedoReyFrancia22kb.txt
Canonicizers:
Normalize Whitespace
EventDrivers:
Character NGrams n : 4
EventCullers:
Most Common Events numevents : 50
Analysis:
Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance
1. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\fernándezOviedoReyFrancia22kb.txt 0.0
2. Alonso de Santa Cruz -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\AlonsodeSantaCruzEmperador22kb.txt 0.022772701060969736
3. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\fernandezOviedo1532catálogo21kb.txt 0.02925992139608724
4. Jerónimo Fernández -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\jeronimofernandezhector1547-5-
17kb.txt 0.03375143172939876
5. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\silva Floriseldeniquea4
proemio18kb.txt 0.0350184864201118
6. Sedeño Summa Varones ilustres 1551 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeño
summaobra10kb.txt 0.03656676042674889
7. Alonso de Santa Cruz -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\AlonsodeSantaCruzReyesCatolicos28kb.txt 0.038664097533087416
8. Hernán Nuñez -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\hernannuñez Trescientas21.txt
0.0387413934531291
9. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\SilvaAmadisdeGrecia foreword13.txt
0.03972023938359015
10. Diego Hurtado de Mendoza -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\diegohurtadodemendoza
granada21kb.txt 0.039747201333175664
11. Pedro Luján -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\PedroLujanLeandro21kb.txt
0.04267350034927164
12. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urrea1523peregrinacion5kb.txt
0.042818007061701024
13. Propaladia 1517 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\propaladiaprologo7kb.txt
0.043784784423560486
14. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\fernandezoviedobatallasProhemio5kb.txt 0.045391539653060864
15. Andrés Laguna -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\andreslagunaObraDioscorides22kb.txt
0.0456866272906431
16. Formacion mujer 1529 Juan Justiniano -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\LuisVivesCristiana1529PrologoDOS14kb.txt 0.04605371688875026

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

17. Villalón Viaje de Turquía -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villalonTurquiaPrologo10kb.txt 0.046960971197812174
18. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Silva Amadis de Grecia foreword8kb.txt 0.04869412822745667
19. Francisco de Encinas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\franciscocodeEnzinasLucioObra20kb.txt 0.04888586885579471
20. Hernán Núñez Trescientas 1499 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\hernannuñeztrescientasprologo7kb.txt 0.0507334703725586
20. Hernán Núñez -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\hernannuñeztrescientasprologo7kb.txt 0.0507334703725586
22. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\EncinaBubolicaPrincipePrologo8kb.txt 0.050818700331707545
23. Pedro Cieza de León -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\pedrociezaleoncartaProhemioPeruk12b.txt 0.05090845261073029
24. Pedro Hernández Villaumbrales -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\hernandezvillaumbralesperegrinacion25kb.txt 0.0509620854556283
25. Cortegana -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CorteganaReyFernandoIII52kb.txt 0.05097957028261535
26. Cuarta Celestina Sancho de Muñón 1542 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\acedopprologo10kb.txt 0.05111879395477936
27. Francisco López de Gomara -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lopezDeGomaraHistoriaGeneralIndias38kb.txt 0.05220960731557622
28. Palmerín 1511 1526 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\palmerin1511prologo10kb.txt 0.05542065721280298
29. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezOviedoHistoriaIndiasitomoProhemio24kb.txt 0.0561673989893261
30. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\EncinaBubolicaReyesPrologo8kb.txt 0.056344031821579765
31. Primaleon 1512 y 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\primaleonprologo4kb1512.txt 0.05877331397049235
32. Amadís 1496 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\AmadisDos21kb.txt 0.05929461257141733
33. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\EncinaCancioneroAlbaPrologo6kb.txt 0.0599108659353238
34. Sedeño Summa Varones ilustres 1551 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeño summaPrologo15kb.txt 0.06149560252053565
35. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\EncinaCancioneroPrincipeProhemio29kb.txt 0.061620879390380856
36. Juan de Timoneda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Timoneda Patrañuela21kb.txt 0.06322613087878337
37. Peregrino 1516 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\peregrino prologo12kb.txt 0.06355687492912343
38. Juan de Pineda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\juandePinedaDialogos29kb.txt 0.06392971104738199
39. Juan de Pineda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\juandePinedaDialogosforeword12kb.txt 0.064066067545990505
40. Bernardino Illán de Alcaraz -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\constitucionesIllan34kb.txt 0.06489756890494569
41. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CristobalCastellejoAulaCortesano21kb.txt 0.06496799232048955
42. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\FernandezOviedoSumarioIndias27kb.txt 0.06516334171899063

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

43. Hernán Pérez de Guzman -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\perezdeguzmanSemblanzas7kb.txt 0.06561971574283376
44. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap20.txt 0.06912522653113029
45. Platir 1533 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Platirprohemio6kb.txt 0.0691501466563017
46. Omero Yliada Prohemio 1519 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\OmeroYliadaProhemio16kb.txt 0.06969505283488409
47. Thebayda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Thebayda Seraphina21kb.txt 0.07125935450940835
48. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap1.txt 0.07162889948984008
49. Sancho de Muñón -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Acevedo Celestina corto42kb.txt 0.07194781986750498
50. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\EncinaCancioneroAlbaHijoPrologo4kb.txt 0.07233693348878256
51. El Cid 1512 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\cidprologo5kb.txt 0.07267853279264003
52. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanacartaexcomunion3kb.txt 0.07271842387860039
53. Conquista de Rodas 1522 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\rodas prologo3kb.txt 0.0728803036966662
53. Conquista de Rodas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\rodas prologo3kb.txt 0.0728803036966662
55. Repetición de amores 1497 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\repeticion amores21kb.txt 0.07288999984235867
56. Fernando de Rojas 1541 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernando de rojas14kb test2.txt 0.07389915776900235
57. Arnalte y Lucenda 1491 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\arnalte incompleta21kb.txt 0.07408469838195508
58. Cartas Sancho de Muñón 1542 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\acevedoamigoautorcartados8kb.txt 0.07457581604478969
59. Thebayda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\thebaida incompleta21kb.txt 0.0752262249513157
60. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezOviedoQuinquagenas28kb.txt 0.07548056704713757
61. Diego Hurtado de Mendoza -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\diegohurtadoCartasPrincipeFelipe38kb.txt 0.07594363296437723
62. Cortegana -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\cortegana asno de oro1543 corto21kb.txt 0.07627496196693251
63. Cartas Sancho de Muñón 1542 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\acevedopoesiacarta2amigoalautor5kb.txt 0.0768794407187241
64. Apiano -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\apiano cosmographicus prologo7kb.txt 0.07715343660622132
65. Escrava 1537 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Escrava1537prologo8kb.txt 0.0776598169828322
66. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lazarillo cuarta33kb.txt 0.07771438052926471
67. Laberinto Boccaccio 1546 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\BoccaccioLaberintoIntroduccion4kb.txt 0.07860959474470797
68. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LazarilloSegundaPartePez21kb.txt 0.07863928643505091
69. Andrés Laguna -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\andreslagunaCatilinarías10kb.txt 0.07867921535301703

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

70. Cuarta Celestina Sancho de Muñón 1542 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\acevedocarta adiegodeacevedo5kb.txt o.07868628247033316
71. Vida y excelentes dichos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\vida y excelentes dichos Prologo7kb.txt o.0793638843890343
72. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezoviedobatalago-13otiene34kb.txt o.07980992288948219
73. Triunfo de amor 1500 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\trionfodeamorprologo4kb.txt o.07996861260080912
73. Triunfo de amor Flores 1495 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\trionfodeamorprologo4kb.txt o.07996861260080912
75. Thebayda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Thebayda ypolita21kb.txt o.08021340150362055
76. Ysopo 1520 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\ysopo prologo1520-7kb.txt o.08072661423594596
77. Gonzalo García de Santa María -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\GarciaSantaMariaCoronicaAragonObra27kb.txt o.08197529260276704
78. Celestina 1501 y 1507 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CelestinaPrologo9kb.txt o.08256216626797241
79. Villalón scholástico -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villalon scholástico primer prologo5kb.txt o.08326415720898273
80. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezOviedoClaribaltePrologo 9kb.txt o.08346840124469335
81. Francisco de Villalobos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villaloboscostumbres humanas21kb.txt o.08354833585811317
82. Cartas Sancho de Muñón 1542 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\acevedocontestacionautoralamigo3kb.txt o.08435104566893514
83. Amadis 1496 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\AmadisUno21kb.txt o.08491182941085051
84. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CristobalCastillejoSermonAmores21kb.txt o.08533441094693162
85. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\FernandezOviedoClaribalte21kb.txt o.08599907215260605
86. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Lazarillo prologo 1620 Juan de Luna 2parte4kb.txt o.086041779359319
87. Baladro Merlin -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\baladroprologo1498-7kb.txt o.08620453238235393
88. Juan Cristóbal Calvete de Estrella -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CalveteEstrellaGonzago12kb.txt o.08632734457632907
89. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezOviedoHistoriaIndiasSextoPrimeraParteProhemio7kb.txt o.08644320393945992
90. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap13.txt o.08670422021530244
91. Consolación Boccaccio 1497 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\boecio1497ConsolacionPrologo9kb.txt o.08677872037704493
92. Pedro de Cieza de León -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\pedrociezaleoncartaReyFelipe5kb.txt o.08680953315789208
93. Jerónimo Fernández -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\jeronimofernandez3año1579-21kb.txt o.0868106212211005
94. Sebastián de Horozco -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sebastiandehorozco cancionero55kb.txt o.08684779734658621
95. Juan Cristóbal Calvete de Estrella -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CalveteEstrellaGonzago10kb.txt o.08745130171296289

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

96. Martín de Córdoba -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\martindecordobaprohemio3kb.txt 0.08752031666324689
97. Palmerín 1511 1526 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\palmerin1511apendice4kb.txt 0.08756850574697062
98. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LazarilloSegundaPartePez56kb.txt 0.08797486255380682
99. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\EncinaCancioneroReyesProhemio7kb.txt 0.08827674125603069
100. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lazarillo21kb primera parte second analysis.txt 0.08868455843720069
101. Francisco de Villalobos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\VillalobosAnfitrionPrimerPrologo7kb.txt 0.08874525199834205
102. Francisco de Encinas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\franciscodeEnzinasVaronesGriegos17kb.txt 0.08881248412170828
103. Juan de Timoneda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Timoneda epistoladamas2kb.txt 0.08923017122028176
104. Juan Rodríguez de Florián -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\FlorineaObraEscenas15solo22kb.txt 0.0919814551605459
105. Arce de Otálora -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\ArceOtaloraPalatinoPinciano22kb.txt 0.09227689740247524
106. Juan de Valdés -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Valdes.JuanCartas1-27kb.txt 0.09228731369126475
107. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lazarillo tercer texto49kb.txt 0.09240748594725878
108. Primaleon 1512 y 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\primaleon3libroIntroduccion8kb1534.txt 0.09267664804190523
109. Marco Tulio Oficios 1550 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\MarcoTulioOficiosPrologokb.txt 0.09291508186033148
110. Cristóbal de Villalón -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\vallalon gramatica prohemio13kb.txt 0.0929874235018533
111. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap3.txt 0.09302639105041532
112. Cortegana -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CorteganaAsnoSeville1513--Prohemio4kb.txt 0.0931215643369977
113. Martín de Córdoba -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\martindecordoba19kb.txt 0.09368675883139266
114. Alonso Núñez de Reinoso -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\clareoyfloriseaprologoJuntasTresCartas1552-7kb.txt 0.09414881566696931
115. Fray Luis de Granada -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\luisdegranada1567peccadores.txt 0.09415105719745709
116. Villalón scholástico -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\VillalonScholasticoProhemio4kb.txt 0.09438540915023075
117. Juan Paez de Castro -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\juanpaezdecastroCartas23kb.txt 0.09446397332072365
118. Palmerín 1511 1526 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\palmerin1534prologo5kb.txt 0.09486465241812803
119. Celestina 1501 y 1507 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\carta celestina1501-3kb.txt 0.09518579122431114
120. Primaleon 1512 y 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\primaleon1534introducciontomo2-3kb.txt 0.0958449771919706
121. Formacion mujer 1529 Juan Justiniano -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LuisVivesCristiana1529PrologoReinaCatalina17kb.txt 0.09594868333742501

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

122. Juan Rodríguez de Florián -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\FlorineaProemio5kb.txt
0.09606669117240763
123. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\FernandezOviedo1535H.GeneralTomo1Libro4Prohemio7kb.txt 0.09687063267978324
124. Vision delectable 1511 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\vision deleitableprologo5kb.txt
0.09739162057160833
125. Itinerario Varthema 1522 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\itinerario varthema prologo
6kb.txt 0.09743246331275679
126. Cristóbal de Villalón -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Villalon Crotalon prologo 9kb.txt
0.09796462106485071
127. Bartolomé de las Casas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\BartolomeDeLasCasasBrevisimak34b.txt 0.09802814103514146
128. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap2.txt
0.09864383658002873
129. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\silvaproemioduquedealva4kb.txt
0.09886022074753553
130. Petrarca 1510 y 1553 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\petrarcaObregoncarta5kb.txt
0.09916219304591167
131. Apiano -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\apianoobra cosmographicus17kb.txt
0.0991965260325528
132. Marco Tulio Oficios 1550 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\MarcoTulioOficiosPrologoTraductorkb.txt 0.09955623883509779
133. Villalón scholástico -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\ villalon scholástico segundo
prologo5kb.txt 0.09956938637855794
134. Andrés Laguna -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\andreslagunaPestilenciaEpistola7kb.txt
0.09969062692462749
135. Linda Melosina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lindamelosina21kb.txt
0.10005438078905027
136. Pedro Mejía -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\PedroMejiaSilvavarialeccion24kb.txt
0.10035556395410605
137. Lucas Fernández -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lucasfernandez dereniego del
amor21kb.txt 0.1014520478345724
138. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\fernandezOviedoSumarioDedicatoria6kb.txt 0.10163845164663543
139. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap21.txt
0.1019640120317925
140. Celestina 1501 y 1507 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CelestinaComedia-1.txt
0.10209671695337186
141. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lazarillo21kb primera parte.txt
0.10236533444041174
142. Pescara -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\PescaraHistoriaAutorALLector4kb.txt
0.10292613882004942
143. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap10.txt
0.10315885731158236
144. Francisco de Enciso -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\florambel1532DeLucea25kb.txt
0.10336029225468091
145. Sedeño Celestina 1540 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeñocelestinaprologo3kb.txt
0.10346007657570067
146. Clarian landanis libro1 1527 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\clarianlandanis1libro1527prologo10kb.txt 0.10367927965886359
147. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lazarillo quinto24kb.txt
0.10394646848516575

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

148. Petrarca 1510 y 1553 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Petrarca1510Prologo19kb.txt
0.10583844741033277
149. Juan de Timoneda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\TimonedaCaminantes21kb.txt
0.10593455561749676
150. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\CristobalCastillejoFarsaConstanca8kb.txt 0.10687065785898431
151. Cristóbal de Villalón -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Villalon Tragedia de Mirrha21.txt
0.10784135563253872
152. Villalón Viaje de Turquía -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villalonTurquia21.txt
0.10808392880850015
153. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap9.txt
0.10825353542295812
154. Sedeño Celestina 1540 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeño celestina prologo7kb.txt
0.10843116979120326
155. Ambrosio de Montesinos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\ambrosiodemontesinosepistola13kb.txt 0.1084471831065914
156. Molina de amor -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\molinadeamor13kb.txt
0.1086785411042599
157. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\SilvaCelestina1534Proemio2kb.txt
0.1086819298823678
158. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\CristobalCastillejoDialogodeMujeres21kb.txt 0.10891207862012264
159. Celestina 1501 y 1507 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\celestinacoplas4kb.txt
0.10897054366032055
160. Amadis 1533 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\amadis venecia 1533 prohemoio8kb.txt
0.10901270446541533
160. Amadis Venecia 1533 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\amadis venecia 1533
prohemoio8kb.txt 0.10901270446541533
162. Francisco de Encinas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\franciscodeEnzinasLucioLectores6kb.txt 0.10924039532707908
163. Gil Vicente -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\GilVicente Don Duardos18kb.txt
0.10939111607781793
164. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap17.txt
0.10973004228764982
165. Pedro Luján -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\pedrolujanSilvesObra9kb.txt
0.1100415562566247
166. Lopez Yanguas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LopezYanguasConcordia23kb.txt
0.1100447186193817
167. Alonso Núñez de Reinoso -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\clareoyfloriseaCorto21kb.txt
0.11026331246745846
168. Francisco de Villalobos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\VillalobosTresGrandesPrologo3kb.txt 0.11087600424568556
169. Gaspar Gómez de Toledo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\GasparGomezdeToledoForeword4kb.txt 0.11091733761139355
170. Juan Rodríguez de Florián -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\FlorineaDedicacion2kb.txt
0.11129204059678555
171. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Silva lisuarteprologo8kb.txt
0.11199491112269788
172. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urrea1513CancioneroCruxifijo6kb.txt
0.11220641126153141
173. Hernando de Castillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\hernando de castillo-6kb.txt
0.11311947626515206

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

174. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezOviedocatálogo prohemio5kb.txt 0.11320198512285817
175. Cayda Príncipe Boccaccio 1495 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\BoccaccioCaydaForeword11kb.txt 0.11328232450442999
176. Pedro Hernández Villaumbrales -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\hernandezvillaumbralesperegrinacionargumento7kb.txt 0.11422961575175972
177. Poncella 1500 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\poncellaprohemia1-7kb.txt 0.11436110628043661
178. Arnalte y Lucenda 1491 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\arnalte prologo3kb.txt 0.11451407391682722
179. Cartas Sancho de Muñón 1542 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\acevedoamigoAlautorprimercarta4kb.txt 0.11462388401372237
180. Grisel 1495 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\griselprologo2kb.txt 0.11483658307160449
181. Pedro Luján -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\pedrolujancoloquiosforeword5kb.txt 0.11534840090301401
182. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap11.txt 0.11599555412304818
183. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap16.txt 0.11658542005010919
184. Francisco de Villalobos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\VillalobosTresGrandesObra21kb.txt 0.11660710861375956
185. Grimalta 1495 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\grimalte prologo3kb.txt 0.11677970874794441
186. Gil Vicente -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\GilVicenteComediaViudo20kb.txt 0.11715580035509987
187. Pedro Luján -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\pedrolujanColloquiosMatrimoniales33kb.txt 0.11732907630772493
188. Gil Vicente -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\GilVicenteSibila31kb.txt 0.11775512900027463
189. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\encina eglogas antes 1509-53kb.txt 0.11838035034557837
190. Genealogia de los dioses 1532 Boccaccio -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\boccaccioGenealogiaprohemio10kb.txt 0.11973689030968315
191. Thebayda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\theybada versos3kb.txt 0.1209150915582562
192. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap6.txt 0.12114458397651529
193. Sedeño Coloquio Bienaventurança 1544 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeño colloquio-3Bienaventurança-12kb.txt 0.1211696647845899
194. Amadís 1496 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\amadisdegaula1496 prologo8kb.txt 0.12126361190800927
195. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanaepilogo5kb.txt 0.12176739976705753
196. Ilustres Mujeres 1494 Boccaccio -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\BoccaccioIlustresmujeresprologo9kb.txt 0.12223270018063204
197. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urrea1513cancioneroprologo12kb.txt 0.12245949117933652
198. Propaladia 1517 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\propaladiaProemio6kb.txt 0.12277339145397614
199. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap14.txt 0.12280232189910889
200. Villalón Viaje de Turquía -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villalonTurquiadados21kb.txt 0.12310444025961609

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

201. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap4.txt 0.123350751377298
202. Amadis 1533 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\amadis1533Prologocorto1-2kb.txt 0.12342500061282047
203. Jerónimo Fernández -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\belian1580 prologo7kb.txt 0.12377551630412953
204. Gil Vicente -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\GilVicente AutoPastoril1502 16kb.txt 0.12503090126022387
205. Jerónimo Fernández -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\belianis1547-5kb prologo.txt 0.12509804144406567
206. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap8.txt 0.12526412227414008
207. Francisco de Enciso -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Enciso - Dialogo de verdades23kb.txt 0.12947625356707904
208. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CristobalCastellejoAulaCortesanoDedicatoria3kb.txt 0.13056215340766197
209. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CristobalCastillejoAdulaciónProhemio2kb.txt 0.13059494438744157
210. Petrarca 1510 y 1553 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Petrarca1510Epilogo19kb.txt 0.1316121433578269
211. Repetición ajedrez 1497 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\repeticionamores ajedrezprincipiodos9kb.txt 0.13182748638906694
212. Tratado de Fisionomia 1494 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\tratadofisionomiaProemio8kb.txt 0.1319465368567886
213. Alfonso de Valdés -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\valdesAlfonsoCartas21kb.txt 0.13206502546377807
214. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap19.txt 0.13206830597243024
215. Formacion mujer 1529 Juan Justiniano -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LuisVivesCristiana1529PrologoJUNO4kb.txt 0.13316475346462853
216. Juan de Timoneda -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\timoneda damboekintroduction3kb.txt 0.13341634822865678
217. Francisco de Villalobos -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\VillalobosAnfitriónFinalPrologo5kb.txt 0.13523226122792287
218. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap12.txt 0.13538342370048806
219. Celestina 1501 y 1507 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CelestinaMs1520TextoCorrecto27kb.txt 0.13599820974355725
220. Cristóbal Castellejo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\CristobalCastillejoPolefema10kb.txt 0.1365984956961943
221. Quiros -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\quirosañadiciones1154act1-7kb.txt 0.13827341231769064
222. Gonzalo Fernández de Oviedo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\fernandezdeOviedoGranCapitan16kb.txt 0.1396934022804075
223. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozano21kb.txt 0.13969956665740546
224. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap15.txt 0.14108936965550467
225. Primaleon 1512 y 1534 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\primaleonforewordcorto1534-3kb.txt 0.14115698169363078
226. Cristóbal de Villalón -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villalon ingeniosa prologo 2kb.txt 0.1416309919803912

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

227. Quiros -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\quirosantiguoautor1453palabrasAct1-8kb.txt 0.14197744326595496
228. Repetición de amores 1497 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\repamores cartas principio lucena5kb.txt 0.1423212710987285
229. Juan del Encina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\encina1521-8kb.txt 0.1441590153713589
230. Diego Hurtado de Mendoza -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\DiegoHurtadoMendoza1545Aristóteles20kb.txt 0.14501701342371376
231. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urreea1513CancioneroPrologoLuna4kb.txt 0.14564149132294935
232. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urreea1513CancioneroSepultura16kb.txt 0.14640250808362254
233. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap5.txt 0.14662898319849504
234. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap7.txt 0.14748140013272226
235. Sedeño Summa Varones ilustres 1551 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeño summaEpistola4kb.txt 0.14750732678802703
236. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urreea1513CancioneroPrologoAranda5kb.txt 0.14939647583714133
237. Lopez Yanguas -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LopezYanguasMundoMoral18kb.txt 0.14985257262643592
238. Formacion mujer 1529 Juan Justiniano -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\LuisVivesCristiana1529Lector5kb.txt 0.14991476046051333
239. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanadigresion2kb.txt 0.15113316713724778
240. Celestina -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Celestina act1 hasta act21\celestina cap18.txt 0.15161419692789746
241. Cárcel de amor -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\carcelamor incompleto21kb.txt 0.15177692095324513
242. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urreea1513CancioneroOtraCarta3kb.txt 0.15186596284985543
243. Sedeño coloquio amores 1544 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sedeñocolloquioamorescompleto-15kb.txt 0.15551467299074562
244. Coloquio Erasmo 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\Erasmo1528Colloquios5kb.txt 0.15814435526290693
245. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozana tesis21kb.txt 0.15862209967067242
246. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urreea1513CancioneroPrologoBelchite4kb.txt 0.16016220623051902
247. Propaladia 1517 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\propaladiatinelariaCorto21kb palabras.txt 0.16266006260351074
248. Mar de historias 1512 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\GuzmanMarHistoriasPrologo5kb.txt 0.16316665872632252
249. Farsa a manera de Tragicomedia -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\farsaAManeraDeTragedia16kb.txt 0.165696972510328
250. Propaladia 1517 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\PropaladiaCalamita21kbCorto.txt 0.1666484653867626
251. Cristóbal de Villalón -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\vallalon piadosolector Provechoso 2kb.txt 0.16721361108622546
252. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozana libro22kb.txt 0.16758904028626753

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

253. Grisel 1495 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\grisel introduccion2kb.txt
0.17029820178984212

254. Gaspar Gómez de Toledo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\gaspargomezdeToledoObra23kb.txt 0.1732050885394928

255. Repeticion ajedrez 1497 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\repcionamores
ajedrezprincipioreglaprimer6kb.txt 0.1768206924363661

256. Propaladia 1517 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\propaladia
himeneaespañol21kbCorto.txt 0.17710074842151802

257. Dialogos Cristianos 1533 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\PerezChinconLenguaErasmusPrologo12kb.txt 0.17855012620418886

258. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\SilvaCelestina1534Coplas3kb.txt
0.1818955199814698

259. Villena 1499 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\villeanaproemio1499 - 8 kb.txt
0.18396000373120192

260. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanadicatoria2kb.txt
0.18469710837515463

261. Antonio Diez -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\antoniodiezClarindo36kb.txt
0.18547313064220328

262. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanaapologia6kb.txt
0.18670370495737243

263. Feliciano de Silva -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\silva Celestina otro 21kb.txt
0.1872237412740041

264. Propaladia 1517 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\propaladiaaquilana21kbCorto.txt
0.1874299876003056

265. Cortegana -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\corteganamiseriacortesanosPrologo2kb.txt
0.19048139529321506

266. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanaepistola3kb.txt
0.19451807757392847

267. Hiseo 1500 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\cartahiseolabrunda6kb.txt
0.19750063281639196

268. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanaexplicacion2kb.txt
0.20083593243364684

269. Cortegana -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\corteganamiseriacortesanos21kb.txt
0.20172920868149202

270. Petrarca 1510 y 1553 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\Petrarca1553VidaSolitariaPetrarcaPrologo7kb.txt 0.20518366113548647

271. Lazarillo -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lazarilloPrimeroprologo2kb.txt
0.21579143115961796

272. Cárcel de amor 1492 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\carceldeamor prologo2kb.txt
0.21678815073683122

272. Cárcel de amor -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\carceldeamor prologo2kb.txt
0.21678815073683122

274. Urrea -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\urrea1513CancioneroSuMujer9kb.txt
0.21829720075231185

275. Sergas esplandian 1510 1526 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\sergasesplandian
prologo1526-4kb.txt 0.22136859841719547

276. Lozana Andaluza 1528 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo 19.11.2019\lozanaargumento3kb.txt
0.2736453319893961

277. Quarino mezquino 1512 -C:\Users\Govert\Desktop\Signatura comienzo
19.11.2019\guarinomezquinoprologo3kb.txt 0.27410029772012967